

Continuous Curing of Thick Composite Cylinders

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ABSTRACT

A new manufacturing technique called *continuous curing* is discussed and analyzed. This method is especially suited to the manufacture of thick composite materials in which thermal spiking is a common problem. Thermal and cure fronts are propagated in the thickness direction as material is accreted on the outer surface. An experimental apparatus was designed and built for use with a filament winder to continuously cure thick composite rotors. A demonstration experiment was carried out using AS4/3501-6 graphite/epoxy prepreg tow. A composite rotor with 152 mm wall thickness was manufactured and embedded thermocouples were monitored throughout the cure process. Results indicate that significant heat flow occurred along the axis of the mandrel and the cure front stagnated 100 mm through the thickness. Full scale mechanical testing is being carried out on the rotor to characterize mechanical performance.

INTRODUCTION

There are several inherent difficulties in the manufacture of thick thermosetting polymer composites. Their low thermal conductivity across the thickness presents a large thermal barrier during heat-up and cool down. During a typical cure cycle the interior temperature of a thick section will lag far behind the surface temperature, causing the surface regions to cure more quickly. If they cure too quickly and gel before the interior is consolidated, the excess resin in the interior is trapped. This leads to non-uniform fiber volume distribution and excessive void growth in the resin-rich interior.

Perhaps the most detrimental behavior observed during thick composite processing is thermal spiking. As the interior heats up, the exothermic curing reaction is initiated and releases energy. This heat is essentially trapped in the interior due to poor thermal conductivity. The entrapped heat raises the temperature of the interior even further, promoting faster curing and more rapid energy release. The process can quickly become unstable, producing a thermal spike. Peak temperatures during a thermal spike are quite high and can easily lead to matrix degradation [1,2]. Very slow heat-up rates and several intermediate dwells are sometimes used to control thermal spiking. Such cure methods lengthen the processing time and increase the manufacturing cost.

Conventional processing techniques are unsuitable for thick composites fabrication due to the thermal spiking and consolidation problems. A new processing technique that address these problems from a fundamental perspective is the *continuous curing method* shown schematically in Fig. 1. Both the physical placement of the precursor material and the curing reaction occur continuously and simultaneously. Since this manufacturing method combines the lay-up and curing processes, total fabrication times can be greatly reduced.

To begin the process, an initial thickness of material is placed onto a heated mold surface. After a short transient heating period, material is supplied continuously to the surface at a constant rate,

characterized by an accretion velocity V . The temperature distribution soon achieves a stable shape, like that shown in Fig. 1b. This curve propagates through the thickness while retaining its shape. A thermal front can be defined by some minimum temperature at which curing occurs. The location of this thermal front propagates through the thickness at a steady speed V_t . Once the material has been heated to this temperature, curing begins and heat is released by the exothermic cure reaction. Under stable conditions the cure distribution has a shape similar to the thermal distribution, but is shifted back a small distance. The cure front is defined as the position where the degree of cure reaches some acceptable value. Under stable conditions this cure front propagates through the thickness at a constant speed V_c .

Figure 1. Continuous Curing Process Schematic

Once the initial start-up period has passed and the thickness of material has built-up to some appreciable level, the curing material is essentially insulated from the mold surface. Thus, the energy to propagate the thermal and cure fronts is obtained directly from the exothermic cure reaction. Curing will continue as long as fresh material is added to the outer surface; the process becomes thermally self-sustaining.

The objectives for continuous curing are first to match the velocities of the thermal, cure, and material fronts as they progress through the material thickness, and second to maximize these velocities. For example, if $V_c > V$ then the cure reaction is proceeding too fast. In this case the surface may cure to such an extent that the strength of interlayer bonds is compromised. In addition, consolidation may be adversely affected if insufficient time is allowed for excess resin and/or voids to flow to the surface. If $V_c \ll V$ then thermal spiking can occur and the cure process will be lengthy. Also, if $V_t \gg V_c$ then conditions are suitable for thermal spiking. Clearly, the proper choice of processing conditions is needed to balance thermal, cure, and material front velocities during continuous curing.

The most suitable manufacturing environment for continuous curing is filament winding. A similar technique for simultaneous winding and curing has been discussed by Korotkov and co-workers [3]. The continuous curing process during filament winding differs from "cure on the fly" filament winding in that the primary curing takes place below the surface, and consolidation may take place slowly in the uncured layer on the surface. The continuous, automated nature of the material placement suits the needs of continuous curing, as well as providing favorable economics. The pretension of fiber tows as they are wound onto the part surface can provide consolidation and suppress voids. Hot pressing can also be adapted to continuous curing by periodically opening the press to add new material.

In this paper analysis of the continuous curing method is presented along with an example fabrication of a thick graphite/epoxy rotor manufactured using this method. The full characterization of the mechanical performance of this rotor is currently being undertaken, however, preliminary observations can be made.

ANALYSIS

In the analysis the following assumptions are made:

- All material properties (specific heat, density, thermal conductivity) are constant during the cure process, independent of cure state and temperature.
- Temperature and degree of cure are functions only of time and direction normal to the part surface.
- Material deformation during the curing process is negligible.
- Heat convection due to resin flow is negligible.
- The radius of curvature of the part is small compared to its thickness.

A schematic of the model geometry is shown in Fig. 2. With these assumptions the heat transfer during the process is described by the coupled energy balance and reaction rate expressions,

$$\rho C_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = k \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} + \rho \gamma H_R \frac{dc}{dt} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{dc}{dt} = f(c, T) \quad (2)$$

The variables ρ , C_p , and k are the density, specific heat, and transverse thermal conductivity for the composite. The last term in Eqn (1) represents the heat generation from curing. The total heat of reaction is H_R and the resin mass fraction is γ . The cure state of the material is characterized by the degree of cure, c . The form of the cure rate expression in Eqn (1) is dependent on the type of resin system used. Many commonly-used phenomenological models have an Arrhenius temperature dependence, i.e.

$$\frac{dc}{dt} = Z \exp\left(\frac{-\Delta E}{RT}\right) f(c) \quad (3)$$

A generalized boundary condition formulation [2] is applied to the inner and outer surfaces to account for either specified surface temperature, finite surface heat flux, adiabatic surface, or convective surface conditions.

$$a_k \frac{\partial T_s(t)}{\partial x} + b_k T_s(t) + c_k T_\infty(t) = d_k \quad k = \text{inner, outer} \quad (4)$$

The coefficients a_i , b_i , c_i , and d_i are constants that depend on the type of boundary condition. The variables $T_\infty(t)$ and $T_s(t)$ are the ambient temperature and the temperature of the boundary surface, respectively. The degree of cure at the outer surface is specified as

$$c(L(t), t) = c_o \quad (5)$$

The initial conditions for temperature and degree of cure are specified throughout the geometry as

Figure 2. Model Geometry

Figure 3. Thickness Accretion History

$$T(x, 0) = T_0 \quad (6)$$

$$c(x, 0) = c_0 \quad (7)$$

The problem posed is a moving boundary problem since during the filament winding process material is added to the outer surface in discrete layers. The thickness of the cylinder at any given location will increase in a stepwise manner as shown in Fig. 3. The outer surface of the cylinder moves with time and its location can be expressed mathematically as

$$L(t) = L_0 + \Delta L \sum_{k=1}^n H(t - i\Delta t_L) \quad (8)$$

Here $H(t)$ is the Heavyside step function, L_0 is the initial thickness, ΔL is the thickness increment, and Δt_L is the time increment. Note that $\Delta L/\Delta t_L$ is the average material accretion rate V . The total number of increments N can be found from the following relation

$$N = \frac{L_f - L_0}{\Delta L} \quad (9)$$

where L_f is the final thickness. There are no general analytical solutions for this model. Instead, numerical solution procedures must be developed to obtain cure and temperature profiles throughout the curing process.

EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP

An experimental apparatus was designed and constructed to manufacture thick composite rotors using the continuous curing method. A heated mandrel was incorporated with an En-Tec Model 5K24-060-4 four-axis filament winder. The mandrel system is shown in Fig. 4. A 102 mm O.D. stainless steel tube was fitted with a 15.9 mm diameter firerod heater (1500 W). The ends of the tube were capped with ceramic insulators and coupled to 76 mm O.D. aluminum extension rods. Power is supplied to the heater through copper slip rings and carbon brushes at one end of the tube. A P.I.D. controller measures the tube surface temperature and cycles power to the heater.

The entire assembly is placed into the mandrel chucks on the filament winder. A photo of this assembly during fabrication of a rotor is shown in Fig. 5.

Figure 4. Heated Mandrel System for Continuous Curing During Filament Winding

Figure 5. Experimental Set-up During Manufacturing of the Composite Rotor

A demonstration experiment was conducted using AS4/3501-6 graphite/epoxy prepreg tow. A composite rotor measuring 152 mm in thickness and 100 mm in length was manufactured. Special care was taken to prevent thermal losses along the axial direction so that a one-dimensional thermal model would be appropriate. The composite rotor and mandrel assembly is shown in schematic form in Fig. 6. A photo of the rotor after fabrication is shown in Fig. 7.

Figure 6. Composite Rotor and Mandrel Assembly Schematic

Figure 7. Composite Rotor After Manufacturing

RESULTS

There were indications during the processing that significant heat flow was occurring along the mandrel axis. The temperature distributions measured from the embedded thermocouples at several different times is shown in Fig. 8. Predictions based on the model are also shown in Fig. 9. The lack of correlation was unexpected and troublesome. Previous experiments utilizing a hot press have shown good agreement [4]. Subsequent analysis has shown that the cure front velocity is extremely sensitive to the ratio of heat transfer coefficient to thermal conductivity at the surface of the rotor. Adequate correlation to the present experimental data was obtained by increasing this ratio by as little as 2%. The cure distribution at the end of winding is shown in Fig. 10. The cure front has propagated about half way through the thickness. Final curing must be carried out in an autoclave or oven.

Overall quality of the rotor is good through the first 1/2 to 2/3 thickness, however the outer layers show significant waviness and lack of consolidation. This is indicative of loss of fiber tensioning and lack of resin flow for the outer regions of the rotor. In fact, the outer regions never reached sufficient temperature to induce flow.

Full scale mechanical testing of the rotor is now being undertaken. Mechanical specimens are being cut from the rotor to characterize the through-thickness stiffness and strength. These results will be reported once testing is completed.

CONCLUSIONS

A continuous curing demonstration experiment utilizing filament winding was conducted. The results were partially successful. Nearly 2/3 of the 152 mm thickness was fully cured after winding, however, the cure front did not propagate any further. We attribute this to thermal diffusion along the axis of the mandrel. This represents an unmodeled heat loss in the one-dimensional thermo-chemical model; some of the exothermic energy released during cure will be bled off into the bulk material and less is available to heat new material as it is placed on the surface. The end result is a suppression of the thermal front velocity and, eventually, a stagnation of the cure front. Modifications to the process to include these effects now include: a 2-D axisymmetric thermo-chemical model, non-conductive annular disk around the rotor, and heat lamp to elevate the environmental temperature.

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Figure 8. Experimental Thermal Distributions during Processing

Figure 9. Model Thermal Distributions during Processing

Figure 10. Degree of Cure of Rotor after Processing